

ENERGY SAVING POTENTIAL IN MUNICIPAL WATER SUPPLY & WASTEWATER SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

Electricity is a scarce commodity in developing countries. It is therefore most important to save electrical energy by avoiding wasteful consumption; which does not mean sacrificing, but maintaining standard services by consuming less energy with the help of energy efficient equipments; which in turn helps the environment by reducing the consumption of fossil fuels. This results in the reduction in operating cost to the Local Body. The saved electricity can be allotted to other needy consumers. Thus, it will solve electric scarcity up to a certain extent.

Urban Local Body (ULB) consumes enormous amount of electricity to provide services to the citizens such as Street lighting, Water Supply and Wastewater Disposal, etc. On an average all these services consume 12% to 15% budgetary provisions to pay electricity bills, which amounts to millions of rupees. If ULBs save even a small percentage of (about 20%) electrical consumption, then millions of rupees can be saved which can be utilized for improving the services. This electricity consumption saving can also help reduce greenhouse gas emissions, as most of the Indian electricity is generated from thermal power stations. {If ULBs in developing countries are made energy efficient, it will help to reduce the impact on the environment globally.}

1.0 BACKGROUND: VADODARA CITY

Vadodara Municipal Corporation (VMC) has a population of 1.4 million and the total area of the city is about 108.27 km². The city corporation has 27 election wards, 10 administrative wards that are divided into four zones.

Regarding the water supply system, the old Vadodara town had a piped water supply since 1894 and piped sewerage since 1896. The first water pumping station and Sewage Treatment Plant were commissioned in April 1952. In fact collection of sewage by pumping was in practice prior to 1952. At present electricity consumption for Vadodara city water and wastewater services are as follows;

1. Sayaji Sarovar (Reservoir) at Ajwa 25 km from the city (east) on the river Vishwamitri, which stores 53.29 mcm, water at its FRL, The city is drawing 70 MLD water, which is about 25% of the source. Water flows from Sayaji Sarovar to the city by natural gradient therefore it does not consume any electrical energy.
2. VMC has constructed four French wells on the river Mahi about 25 to 30 km away from the city (towards north). VMC is pumping 205 MLD of water from the river. Piped water supply from river Mahi requires high head pumps. Total connected electrical load at all French wells is 4.7 MW, which consumes 28.656 million kWh amounting to Rs. 131.28 millions annually.
Note: French wells are located 25 Kms towards north from the city therefore it requires high head (55 meters to 70 meters) pumps to pump water to the city.
3. 285 MLD water received from the various sources is being distributed in the city through 18-water distribution pumping stations located at various places in the city. All the 18 pumping stations are connected with electrical Contract Demand of 6.51 Mw, which consumes 14.4 million kWh amounting to Rs. 67.95 millions annually.
4. The wastewater generated as a result of various human activities is lifted, collected and treated through 29 lift stations and four Sewage Treatment Plants, which has connected

electrical load of 4.2 MW and consumes 10.386 million kwh amounting to Rs.43.580 million annually.

During the year 1997-98 total electrical energy consumption for water supply & wastewater disposal was 41.184 million kwh amounting to Rs. 160.71 millions, while it is estimated that in the current year (2001-2002) annual consumption will be 53.44 millions kwh worth Rs. 242.95 millions. These figures clearly indicate that there is a 7.5% average annual growth in electrical consumption and 12.5% growth in payment of electrical charges in last four years.

Total electrical consumption of the corporation is amounting to Rs. 320 millions out of which share of water and wastewater services are Rs. 243 millions which is about 75% of the total electrical consumption. This is matching with the worldwide consumption pattern by pump sets for water/wastewater services (As per the discussion with the representatives of Alliance to save energy USA). This consumption tends to increase every year due to increasing population in the city. Looking in to the sizeable share of electrical cost, VMC took a pragmatic decision to carry out energy auditing of all its pumping installations. After due process VMC had appointed M/s Saket Projects Limited, Ahmedabad to carry out energy auditing study.

Prior to the appointment of energy auditor VMC had taken steps to improve "power factor" (p.f.), and reduced Contract Demand and achieved considerable savings by using in-house expertise. Details are mentioned here under:

➤ Pumping stations where power factor has been improved are as under:

Sr. No.	Location	p.f. before improvement	p.f. after improvement	Appropriate savings per annum in Rs. Lacs since 1997.
1	Nalanda Overhead (O/H) Tank	0.80 to 0.75	0.9 to 0.98	6.0
2	Sewasi-gotri O/H tank	0.70 to 0.80	0.9 to 0.98	4.0
3	Tandalja O/H tank	0.50 to 0.60	0.9 to 0.98	8.0
4	Gajrawadi sewage pumping station	0.40 to 0.50	0.9 to 0.98	12.0
5	Atladra sewage pumping station.	0.80 to 0.85	0.9 to 0.98	2.0
Total Annual Savings				Rs.32.00 Lacs

➤ Reduction in Contract demand has been achieved in following overhead tanks:

Sr. No.	Location	Previous Contract Demand	Current Contract Demand after reduction	Appropriate savings per annum in Rs. lacs.
1	Nalanda Overhead (O/H) Tank	750	475	2.4
2	Sewasi-gotri O/H tank	750	475	2.4
3	Tandalja O/H tank	750	475	2.4

Because of the above background, it is essential for the Corporation to take steps to reduce energy consumption; best practice for this is to select energy efficient electrical and mechanical equipments at planning stage. Main energy consumption component in water supply and wastewater disposal is **Motor-Pump** set. Appropriate selection of pump for its application with

correct head range (H) and discharge (Q) can run at its best efficiency, otherwise it leads to inefficient operation and will waste electrical energy.

To measure efficiency of motor-pump set, simultaneous measurements of flow (Q), head (H), and power (KW) is required, which requires precise instruments and expertise. In house facility for the same is not available with the Corporation, therefore the agency had been appointed to carry out energy audit.

The energy audit agency took more than a year for measurement and analysis of operating parameters of almost all the pumping stations. Final report was submitted in December'1998.

2.0 FINDINGS OF THE ENERGY AUDITOR

From the measurement and analysis following reasons were found for inefficient operation of Motor-Pump sets:

- Pump running with throttled valve.
- Selection of higher head than required.
- Because of higher head, pump operates entirely at different duty than at which it should run resulting in inefficient operation.
- Pumps running after expiry of its useful running life, which requires immediate replacement.

Other reasons for inefficient operation of Motor-Pump sets are:

- Poor suction lift.
- Under size suction & delivery pipe.
- High friction loss due to wrong installation of pump delivery pipeline.
- Parallel operation of pumps with different duty conditions.
- Old pumps with lower design efficiency.
- Improper maintenance, by and large preventive maintenance is ignored.
- Lower power factor of electric motor.

Refer Table No. I [Table No. I](#)

3.0 MEASURES IMPLEMENTED AND RESULTS ACHIEVED

Initially VMC has implemented suggestions of the energy auditor in following pumping stations:

- 1) Lalbaug water pumping station, 2) Gajarawadi Sewage Main Pumping Station,
- 2) Atladra Sewage Treatment Plant 4) Shastribridge Sewage Pumping station.

Operating parameters & energy consumption before and after replacement of pumps have been shown in Table No. II

The source of data for the Table No. II is:

- Electricity consumption is taken from the actual GEB electricity bills.
- The various parameters for the pumps are taken from energy audit study.

3.1 Sewage Lift Stations: Gajrawadi and Shastribridge

Sewage lift stations at Gajrawadi and Shastribridge were commissioned in 1968 and in 1978 respectively. During the past three decades alongwith growth in population and sewage generation the pumping capacities were not increased to meet the requirements. Due to insufficient pumping capacity of sewage, the sewer network remained in surcharge condition except during late night hours. This resulted in silting of sludge and choking of sewer lines. At both the locations VMC had selected pumps to discharge more sewage water to improve sanitation conditions in the sewage network area was pertaining to respective lift stations. After commissioning new pumps VMC not only solve surcharge problem of the sewer network but also achieved sizable financial savings as under:

- At Gajrawadi lift station the power saving is 1.862 million kwh amounting to Rs. 8.379 million annually by investing Rs. 2.0 millions with a simple payback period of 3 months only.
- At Shastribridge the power saving is 0.236 million kwh amounting to Rs. 1.062 million annually by investing Rs. 1.2 million with a simple payback period of 14 months.

VMC has implemented the recommendations of the energy audit study with modifications, which were required to overcome the operational difficulties. Thus VMC not only achieved savings more than those identified by the energy audit study, but also improved services.

3.2 Lalbaug overhead tank

Due to increase in the population, the water demand in command area of this water distribution station has increased. Thus it was required to pump more water to maintain the required level of water in the overhead tank in order to supply water to a larger area by maintaining required pressure in the distribution network all the time. VMC replaced two pumps of 150 HP with 300 HP and increased the pump discharge while the energy auditor had suggested to replace one 150 HP pump and one 300 HP pump with the same discharge. By replacing the pumps VMC not only solved the operational difficulties but also saved 0.543 million kwh amounting to Rs. 2.44 million annually at the cost of Rs. 1.2 million with a simple payback period of 6 months.

3.3 Atladra STP

VMC is treating 27 MLD sewage with trickling filter process. Recirculation pumps installed in 1971 were running at 33 to 35% efficiency. Due to lower efficiency of the recirculation pumps the treatment efficiency was poor and the treated effluent was not matching the disposal standards of the Pollution Control Board. After replacement of the recirculation pumps VMC has increased the influent flow by almost 2.5 times and the quality of the treated effluent has improved to match the disposal standards of the Pollution Control Board (i.e. the BOD removal efficiency has improved). Thus by improving the treatment efficiency VMC has saved 0.73 million kwh power amounting to Rs.3.285 million by investing Rs. 1.5 millions with a simple payback period of 6 months.

NOTE: In the service of wastewater disposal VMC have obtained more savings than identified by replacing the pumpsets in three pumping stations only.(The saving is 2.828 million kwh worth Rs. 12.728 millions)

4.0 MEASURES YET TO BE IMPLEMENTED

Energy audit study had suggested to replace 67 nos. of pumps and refurbishment of 67 pumps at the cost of Rs. 30 millions. (The estimate of the energy auditor is of Rs. 20 millions only.) Out of which VMC has replaced only 9 pump sets at the cost of Rs. 5.9 millions. Yet VMC requires implementing the recommendations as mentioned in the Table No. I.

➤ Water source:

As per the recommendations of energy auditor VMC was required to replace 15 pumps at the four French wells (water source) and refurbishment of 9 pumps was required. Looking to the 85 mt. head of the installed pump sets the 9 pump sets suggested for refurbishment will also required to be replaced to achieve better savings than estimated because the operating head range of the French wells is between 55 to 70 mts.

Looking at the maximum contribution in electrical consumption and saving potential VMC had invited tenders to replace the bowl assembly of the vertical turbine pumps by maintaining the existing discharge at lower head. The tenders are under scrutinization stage and will be finalized shortly. After implementing this VMC will be able to achieve further power saving of 4.3 million kwh amounting to Rs. 18 million.

➤ Water Distribution:

Energy auditor had recommended to replace 18 pumps and refurbishment of 47 pumps with a saving potential of 3.15 million kwh amounting to Rs. 14.18 millions with a simple payback period of 10 to 12 months. VMC is on its way to implement this within a year.

➤ **Wastewater Disposal:**

In this service the energy auditor had recommended to replace 34 nos. of pumps and 2 nos. for refurbishment within a saving potential of 2.34 millions kwh amounting to Rs. 10.5 millions. VMC has achieved more savings than estimated by replacing pumps in three sewage lift stations (2.828 million kwh amounting to Rs. 12.726 millions.) In wastewater services the contribution in savings potential of other lift stations are negligible.

5.0 LESSONS LEARNED

Looking at the detailed investigations of all the pumping installations it is observed that the main reason for inefficient operation of the pumps is the improper selection of head. As the heads of the installed pump sets were higher than the system head or required head the pumps were running at duties different from design duty resulting into high power consumption and lower efficiency. Therefore enough care must be taken at the design stage to select proper head range (H in meters) for particular discharge (Q in cubic meter per hour) so that the pumps can operate within its best efficiency zone and can save wasteful energy.

6.0 CONCLUSION

By implementing suggestions of the energy audit study VMC has achieved overall power saving of 3.37 million kwh worth Rs. 15.17 million annually. VMC is also on its way to replace the bowl assembly of two frenchwells and so additional savings of 4.3 million kwh worth Rs. 18 million will be achieved with an investment of Rs. 5.8 millions with a simple payback period of 4 months only. While in water distribution pumping stations and wastewater disposal the recommendations will be implemented within a year. Thus this reduction in the financial burden will help the City Corporation to allocate budgetary provisions to other development works. The reduction in the energy consumption results in the reduction in consumption of various fossil fuels and finally the various GHG (greenhouse gases) emissions. Ultimately, this will also help to improve the environment globally.

Sr No	Location of the pumping station	Efficiency of pump sets		KWH / Kl		Total Annual energy saving (million KWH)	Energy in GJ	Reduction in GHG emissions (CO ₂ in tonnes)
		Before replacement	After replacement	Before replacement	After replacement			
1	Lalbaug overhead tank	50.86-70.51	86	0.198	0.141	0.543	1955	638
2	Gajrawadi sewage pumping station*	12.91-63.26	83	0.173	0.091	1.862	6703	2189
3	Atladra sewage treatment plant	33.43-35.23	83	0.079	0.0327	0.730	2628	858
4	Shastribridge pumping station	42.45	82	0.083	0.049	0.236	850	270
5	Fajalpur and Poicha frenchwells*	48-72	82	-	-	4.3		

*Projected savings, recommendations of the energy audit study yet to be implemented.

APPENDIX**Table No. I Summary of Saving Potential in Water and Wastewater services**

Sr No.	Location	Pump Replacement	Pump refurbishment	Present Bill\Year		Annual Saving Potential	
		No.	No.	Million KWH	Million Rs.	Million KWH	Million Rs.
1	Water source	15	9	28.66	131.40	5.55	24.96
2	Water distribution	18	47	14.40	67.95	3.15	14.18
3	Waste water disposal	34	2	10.38	43.60	2.34	10.53
	Total	67	58	53.44	242.95	11.04	49.67

Looking to the table energy saving potentials are as follows:

- **Water source:** The saving potential is 19.36% amounting to Rs. 24.96 millions which requires investment of Rs. 9 to 11 millions and the payback period is 4 to 6 months.
- **Water distribution :** The saving potential is 19.22% amounting to Rs. 14.18 millions requiring a investment of Rs. 10 to 12 millions for which the payback period is 10 to 12 months.
- **Waste water disposal** The saving potential is 20.37% amounting to Rs. 10.53 millions for which the investment required is Rs. 7 millions with a payback period of 10 to 12 months.
- Thus the overall annual saving potential is 11.04 million kwh amounting to Rs. 49.67 millions which requires an approximate investment of Rs. 30 millions with a payback period of about 7 months.

➤ **TABLE NO. II Comparision of energy consumption before and after replacment of motor pump sets**

BEFORE REPLACEMENTS									
Sr. No.	Location	No of pumps	Power of pump	Operat- ing Hours	Design Head	Operat- ing Head	Flow	Efficiency	Pow consu-
			<i>HP</i>	<i>hrs\day</i>	<i>mt</i>	<i>mt</i>	<i>KL\min</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Milli KW</i>
1	Lalbaug overhead tank	6	4x150 2x300	11	36	29.03	7.45-22.00	50.86-70.51	1.63
2	Gajrawadi sewage pumping station*	6	2x110 2x200 2x250	34	18	9.15	21.13	12.91-63.26	1.3
3	Atladra sewage treatment plant	4	4x50	48	9.15	6.63	6.1	33.43-35.23	0.5
4	Shastribridge pumping station	3	2x60 1x30	19	18	11	10	42.45	0.34
AFTER REPLACEMENTS									
1	Lalbaug overhead tank	6	4x300 2x150	23		37	22.2	86	1.49
2	Gajrawadi sewage pumping station*	6	4x200 2x250	39.3		16	36.66	83	1.43
3	Atladra sewage treatment plant	3	3x50	43		8	30	83	0.51
4	Shastribridge pumping station	3	2x100 1x55	13		11	13.23	82	0.34

* In case of Gajrawadi the power consumption and amount is six months because the pump-sets were commissioned in June'2001 and rest is for 12 months.